

Project Handbook

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Project Handbook

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Executive summary

The FoSSNet project handbook provides an overview of different elements of the project to facilitate the management and coordination of the project. We hope that the project handbook will function as a reference document for partners, a source to easily find information on the project. It is also our hope that the project handbook will be a living document that is updated as we move forward, to make sure that the information is up-to-date and relevant for the implementation of FoSSNet.

Document information

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Revision history

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10/06/2024	V1	FoSSNet Partners	Text adjustments
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1. Introduction

This project handbook provides FoSSNet partners with practical information necessary for participating in the project. The handbook is a living document and will be updated during the lifetime of the project so that the information is always up-to-date and relevant. This document should be used as a companion to the Description of Action (DoA), which outlines the research objectives, work packages, and tasks; the Data Management Plan, which outlines detailed procedures for handling data and the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation plan.

The handbook includes information pertaining to:

- Project structure timeline, infrastructure, and contacts
- Practical requirements and quality control for deliverables
- Plan and principles for peer reviewed publications
- Dissemination routines
- Opportunities for exploitation
- Gender policy
- Research ethics; and
- Data management.

Please note that the handbook does not currently include detailed information on the financial and contractual management of the project. These will be covered in webinars leading up to reporting periods. Questions regarding these aspects of the project should be directed to Project Administrator Svetlana Wolkov (svetlanaw@ruc.dk) who will lead the reporting process.

1.1 Project design, consortium and infrastructure

The following sections give an overview of project consortium and infrastructure.

Key information about the project

Grant number	101134861
Funding program	Horizon Europe
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-4
Funding instrument	Research and Innovation Action
Project officer	Alessandra Sasso (REA/B/04)
Start date	February 1st 2024
End date	January 31st 2028
Grant Amount	5,521,185 EUR
Total person months	488.55

1.2 Project objectives and logic

This section provides an overview of FoSSNet's Specific Objectives (SO) and the project logic. Please consult the Description of Actions (DoA) for more detailed information on the objectives.

FoSSNet's Specific Objectives (SO) are:

- SO1: Develop a conceptual framework and a process for developing food system transformation pathways.
- SO2: Establish, mobilise and consolidate an inclusive inter- and transdisciplinary pan-European academic network for food systems science.
- SO3: Enhance inclusivity of the Knowledge and Innovation system for a sustainability transformation of EU food systems
- SO4: Co-produce research for sustainable food system transformation
- SO5: Build Food Systems Capability
- SO6: Create impact through dissemination, communication and exploitation

Figure 1 Project design and work packages

1.3 Project-months-to-calendar months converter

Table 1 Project Months to Calendar Months Converter

M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
FEB24	MAR24	APR24	MAY24	JUN24	JUL24	AUG24	SEP24	OCT24	NOV24	DEC24	JAN25
M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
FEB25	MAR25	APR25	MAY25	JUN25	JUL25	AUG25	SEP25	OCT25	NOV25	DEC25	JAN26
M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
FEB26	MAR26	APR26	MAY26	JUN26	JUL26	AUG26	SEP26	OCT26	NOV26	DEC26	JAN27
M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48
FEB27	MAR27	APR27	MAY27	JUN27	JUL27	AUG27	SEP27	OCT27	NOV27	DEC27	JAN28

1.4 Project Timeline (Milestones and Deliverables)

Number	Title	WP	Lead	Deadline (M)
D6.2	FoSSNet Website	6	EUFIC	5
D6.1	DEC Strategy	6	EUFIC	6
D7.1	Project handbook incl. quality, gender, and ethics guidelines	7	RUC	6
D7.2	Data Management Plan	7	RUC	6
M13	Early-stage promotional toolkit	6	EUFIC	6
D1.1	Food System Conceptual Framework	1	UOXF	9
M8	Launch of pan-european survey on research needs and knowledge gaps in food systems science (T4.1)	4	ULUND	12
M7	A monitoring and evaluation framework for assessing inclusivity and inter- and transdisciplinary co-learning (T3.3)	3	STICHTING VU	14
M1	Literature review and search of existing data on the EU food system, based on T1.1 (T1.2.1)	1	UOXF	15

M2	Template developed to identify methods, tools and models for food system transformation science (1.3.1)	1	ULUND	15
M3	Potential scope and depth of a pan-EU network for food systems science identified through a Social networks analysis (T2.1.2)	2	ULUND	15
M6	Case Study Synthesis report of T3.1 and T3.2	3	RUC	15
D3.2	Concept for a toolkit for transdisciplinary research	3	BSC	18
D4.1	Research Agenda and roadmap for FSS	4	ULUND	18
D5.2	Higher Education Food Systems Curricula	5	ULUND	18
D6.3	1st Dissemination, comm and networking activities	6	EUFIG	18
M10	1st Summer School FoSSNet	5	EIT FOOD	19
M9	1st workshop takes place in territorial Labs (T4.2)	4	UB	20
D3.1	Analysis of exclusion mechanisms in FOKIS	3	RUC	24
D6.6	1st Conf. proceedings advancing FSS	6	EUFIG	24
M11	Analysis and evaluation of food system curricula	5	ULUND	24
D2.1	Social Network Analysis report	2	ULUND	25
D1.2	Food Systems Map	1	UOXF	30
D3.3	Toolkit for transdisciplinary research	3	BSC	30
D6.8	FoSSNet Exploitation Plan	6	EIT FOOD	30
D4.2	Participatory research methodology	4	UB	32
D5.1	Food systems literacy framework	5	EIT FOOD	32
D5.3	Ready to use Next generation food system curricula	5	ULUND	36
D6.4	2nd Dissemination, comm and networking activities	6	EUFIG	36

M5	Food systems science seminars (3) in Eastern Europe (T2.2.3)	2	IRWIR PAN	36
D1.3	Food systems transformation Framework	1	ULUND	40
D4.3	Interdisciplinary insights into the true cost of food	4	WR	40
M12	Pilot test of new curricula	5	ULUND	40
D3.4	Roadmaps for inclusive research and innovation system in FSS	3	STICHTING VU	42
M4	Hackathons (T2.2.2)	2	EIT FOOD	43
D4.4	Policy briefs on food systems science policy interfaces	4	UB	46
D2.2	Knowledge Hub process report	2	BLE	48
D2.3	Value proposition and legacy of FoSSNet	2	EIT FOOD	48
D6.5	3rd Dissemination, comm and networking activities	6	EUFIC	48
D6.7	2nd Conf. proceedings advancing FSS	6	EUFIC	48
D6.9	Final FoSSNet Exploitation Plan	6	EIT FOOD	48

1.5 Reporting periods

Reporting Period	Start -end months	Deadline for input from Partners	Review Meeting
1	M1 - M18	M19	M21
2	M19-M36	M37	M39
3	M37-M48	M49	M48

The project has 60 days to submit the Periodic Report after the end of the reporting period.

The Periodic Report consists of a technical and a financial part, respectively.

Technical report

WP Leaders are responsible for collecting and filling in the data for the Technical part

of the report in ECAS. 30 days before the reporting deadline, the Technical report should be sent to the coordinator for review.

Financial report

Each partner is responsible for producing its own Financial report. The signed Financial reports must be submitted to the coordinator 15 days before the reporting deadline. The coordinator then submits the Periodic Report to the EC.

Review by the European Commission

After the Periodic report is submitted, a review meeting will take place. The Project Officer revises the report and can ask for additional information and explanations. After the Periodic report has been approved, the EC issues the interim payment.

Overview: Monitoring and Reporting

Figure 2 Monitoring and reporting in Horizon Europe Projects (European Commission)

1.6 Project Infrastructure

<p>Coordinator Contacts</p>	<p>Stine Rosenlund Hansen (PI/Coordinator) stroha@ruc.dk Svetlana Wolkow (Administrative Coordinator) svetlanaw@ruc.dk Jo Krøjer (Gender Advisor) Catharina Juul Kristensen (Ethics Advisor)</p>
<p>Consortium mailing lists</p>	<p>To be developed</p>

Microsoft Teams Space	All detailed project information is shared on the FoSSNet Teams space
Social Media Accounts	LinkedIn: @FoSSNet X (Twitter): @SciFoodHealth
Hashtag (s)	#FoSSNet

2. Deliverables

2.1 Practical requirements

Please make sure that the deliverable documents follow the following requirements:

- Use the template for deliverables accessible on SharePoint.
- Please do not make changes to the style or font size.
- Use header styles in the template
- Do not use a font size smaller than 11, standard font should be 12
- For illustrations, graphs and graphics, follow colour code guidelines in the template

2.2 Quality Control

To ensure the quality of the deliverables and avoid delays, the overall content and structure of the deliverable should be agreed by those involved in its production.

In addition, 2 internal reviewers should be identified early in the process and deliverables should be sent to reviewers at least one month before the deadline.

Make sure that the deliverable is in compliance with the plan set out in the DoA to make it easy for the Commission to check and/or that explanations for any deviations from the plan are clearly communicated.

Similarly, any ethics and data management issues relevant for the submission of publicly available deliverables (check the DoA) should be managed well before the submission deadline.

3. Peer-reviewed publications

FoSSNet's deliverables draw upon the work of a large number of consortium members. Interests and incentives to publish in peer-reviewed academic journals and other types of publication forums of these members are diverse. It is important that the publications' format and authorship are coordinated within the project with a focus on the needs that PhD students and early career researchers have e.g. in relation to first authorship. FoSSNet will strive to develop a fair and inclusive strategy for peer reviewed articles and authorship.

A publication policy will be developed and the handbook will be updated accordingly.

This deals with:

- Authorship including opt-in requirements and authorship duties.
- Early career researchers roles and opportunities
- Conflict
- Publication plan and processes for transparency around publication

3.1 Publications and FAIR

To ensure that FoSSNet lives up to its obligations to produce science that is “as open as possible”, all planned peer reviewed publications should be either gold (preferable) or green open access.

In addition, data (when appropriate) and metadata for individual data sets should be shared through an applicable repository (see section 8 and the Data Management Plan). The open data will be licensed under the Creative Commons CC-BY-ND (Attribution-No Derivatives).

All publications must respect the terms of consent of data subjects. Since these may vary from country to country, it is imperative that authors consult these terms before making use of available data.

4. Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation

All FoSSNet partners must communicate, disseminate and exploit the project's results, respecting the rules foreseen in the Grant Agreement and respecting the guidelines provided by the EU, for instance in terms of acknowledgement of funding.

Such activities will be executed on the basis of a strategy defined in the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (D6.1), that defines activities, modalities, timeline and responsibilities for their implementation, such as ways to report the work done and how to revise the strategy. All the partners will be involved under the EUFIC coordination (for the communication and dissemination activities), the EIT Food guidance on the exploitation actions and the RUC supervision, as a project coordinator.

In particular, partners are expected in contributing to the following actions:

- Implementing communication, dissemination and exploitation activities within the networks they belong to, in their own countries and at the European level;
- Engaging stakeholders belonging to the identified target audiences in a meaningful and coordinated way;
- Mapping events and providing news and updates for the FoSSNet website and social media;
- Participating in a coordinated way at conferences, workshops, events, etc. to promote the project and its outcomes;
- Requesting support for communication and dissemination materials (flyers, save the date for events, factsheets, etc.) proactively and on time;
- Keeping track of all activities implemented, aimed to show the consortium outreach and address the expected outcomes and impacts planned.

The coordination of the activities will happen through the WP Leaders/Executive Committee meetings and, when needed, with the organisation of ad hoc meetings aiming to organise specific activities or to solve issues.

In order to keep track of the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, a reporting scheme was prepared and integrated into the FoSSNet SharePoint. The structure and the instructions on how to use it is presented in a video recorded by EUFIC and available to partners on SharePoint. Moreover, EUFIC is sending monthly reminders to partners asking to fill in the reporting scheme.

In principle, FoSSNet partners should enter data in SharePoint as soon as they implement an activity. EUFIC will monitor the process and, in any case, it will contact all partners reminding them of their duties:

- Before every annual meeting, to discuss possible fine-tuning of the strategy in a dedicated session;
- For the reporting period fixed by the EC, to update data to the preparation of the technical report;
- By July 2025, January 2027 and January 2028, when updated versions of D6.1 and the final report on activities performed must be delivered.

For additional and more detailed information, partners should read and know the provisions in D6.1

5. Gender and Diversity

Gender equality and diversity in general play key roles in FoSSNet both in terms of governance, development of the project and building a gender dimension into the research that is conducted. Attention to gender and inclusion more broadly are guiding principles for advancing food systems science and building a scientific network.

A Gender and Diversity Policy (GDP) will be developed with guidelines on how gender and diversity is to be approached in FoSSNet. Here, it will amongst others be elaborated how the below focus on gender will be broadened to include other diversity aspects.

With regards to gender equality there are two overall aspects to consider: Gender balance and gender dimension (EC ND, Gender equality in research and innovation¹). The FoSSNet GDP will include both. These aspects apply to other inclusion criteria as well.

The policy will amongst others include issues of

- Creating awareness
- Recruitment (internal and external)
- Work distribution
- Decision-making
- Meeting dynamics
- Representation
- Outreach, events and dissemination
- Gender and diversity as analytical perspectives

5.1 Resources

Gender advisor

Jo Krøjer (RUC) is the gender advisor and will advise the project coordinator from a gender perspective. Furthermore, the Gender advisor will promote dialogue on gender issues with the WP leaders.

The European Commission's strategy for gender equality: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en#gender-mainstreaming-through-the-integration-of-the-gender-dimension-in-research-and-innovation-content

¹ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en#the-commissions-gender-equality-strategy

6. Ethics and research integrity

6.1 Principles

The following list presents the overall ethical principles relevant to the methodologies used in the project. Updated research guidance will be produced and provided in connection with research approvals (section 6.2)

Informed consent

A free, informed and explicit consent is both an ethical and a legal requirement (see “GDPR”, EU 2016/679) to process personal data. In case of data collection for the FoSSNet project, informed consent shall be obtained as required by national, European or international law or regulation; templates for the informed consent forms will be provided by work package leaders, based on a template provided by the coordinator. If necessary, this must be adjusted to comply with national and/or institutional requirements and potentially translated by each partner.

If students or other non-scientific staff have access to data, this should clearly be stated in the informed consent.

Personal information

All research activities that may record sensitive personal information will be conducted following the highest standards of personal data protection, incl. the GDPR. This includes, but is not exclusive to, the use of pseudonymization/anonymization, avoiding direct quotation if not scientifically necessary, and protecting data from re-identification through secure storage.

Research integrity

All research activities will follow the principles outlined in the European Code of Conduct of Research Integrity (ALLEA 2017) and the Ethics Guidance for Social Science and the Humanities issued by the European Commission (EC 2018) with regards to SSH research. This involves, but is not exclusive to, designing research protocols to avoid intentional or unintentional psychological or social harm in any form, as well as clearly outlining easily applicable mechanisms for informants to opt out before, during, or after these activities.

6.2 Ethics approvals

The overall ethics approval will be conducted by The Research Ethics Committee at Roskilde University representing RUC’s Institutional Review Board. The overall review has been initiated and an updated guidance based on the result will be included in revisions of the handbook.

Beyond adhering to the overall ethics approval, partners must follow their institutional ethics approval procedures. Be aware that these procedures must be concluded before data collection.

Publication

Authors must ensure that the use of the data is “FAIR” (i.e., as open as possible, as closed as necessary), particularly with regard to the terms of consent given (anonymization; pseudonymization) taken into the account the risks to data subjects from re-identification through contextual data (position in organization; type of job in a region; acts performed in public; etc.). This is particularly relevant regarding the use of “rich” qualitative data.

7. Data Management

Each partner is responsible for adherence to GDPR, EU and national requirements related to data management.

Data management will be guided by FAIR principles and the mantra of making data “as open as possible and as closed as necessary” as follows:

- **Findable** - Making data findable, including provisions for metadata
- **Accessible** - Making data accessible for future use
- **Interoperable** - Making data interoperable by harmonizing data according to standards where possible
- **Reusable** – Taking steps to make data reusable where possible

For more detailed information on data management requirements, please see D1.2 Data Management Plan.

7.1 Internal data sharing and storage

Some data will contain sensitive information that cannot be shared across the full body of consortium members. In this case, access to data or folders will be restricted to necessary consortium members using password protection.

Guidelines on internal data sharing will follow here.

Storage

Raw data and data containing personal or sensitive information must be stored in a storage solution that is password secured, encrypted, and hosted on a European

server. Data stored on Portable drives i.e. flash drives and laptops should be encrypted until data can be sorted on a safe server.